

A Study to Evaluate Patient Satisfaction After Implementation of Respectful Maternity Care Under Laqshya Programme at Tertiary Care In Central India

Dr. Nikita Mandloi¹, Dr. Kavita N Singh², Dr. Sakshi Mishra³

¹Post Graduate, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, NSCB Medical College, Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh, India

²Dean, Gandhi Medical College, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India and Former Head of Department, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, NSCB Medical College, Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh, India

³Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, NSCB Medical College, Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh, India

OPEN ACCESS

*Corresponding Author:

Dr. Nikita Mandloi

Post Graduate, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, NSCB Medical College, Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh, India

Received: 02-07-2025

Accepted: 22-07-2025

Available Online: 02-08-2025

©Copyright: IJMPR Journal

ABSTRACT

Aims: This study evaluates the satisfaction levels among mothers after the implementation of RMC under the LaQshya Programme at tertiary care in Central India.

Method and materials: This study was designed as a cross-sectional observational study. A cross-sectional study design was selected to capture a snapshot of the satisfaction levels of mothers who delivered at a tertiary care centre in Central India.

Result: The study evaluated patient satisfaction with various maternity services. Most participants gave moderate scores (3) for registration (70%), information on facility access (39.5%), bedsheets (62.6%), food (75.9%), and wheelchair/aya bai assistance (~73%). Registration was initiated within 30–60 minutes for 40.1% of women. During delivery, 94.37% reported no abuse, 91% had adequate privacy, 94% received delivery information, and 94.09% had a birth companion. Breastfeeding was mostly delayed, with 57.8% initiating after 2 hours. Contraceptive advice was received by 78.1% of participants. Overall, while satisfaction was moderate, gaps remained in timely registration, early breastfeeding initiation, and postnatal contraceptive counseling.

Conclusion: In order to address the identified gaps and enhance the overall quality of maternity care, it is crucial to prioritize continuous training for healthcare providers, allocate resources more effectively, and establish strong monitoring mechanisms.

Keywords: Respectful maternity care (RMC), LaQshya .

INTRODUCTION

Maternal and neonatal health remains a significant public health challenge, particularly in developing countries like India, where maternal and neonatal mortality rates are relatively high. Despite various interventions and programmes aimed at improving maternal health outcomes, the quality of care during childbirth continues to be a critical area needing improvement. Respectful Maternal Care (RMC) has emerged as a crucial aspect of maternal healthcare, aiming to ensure that women receive dignified, respectful, and high-quality care during childbirth. This study evaluates the satisfaction levels among mothers after the implementation of RMC under the LaQshya Programme at a tertiary care centre in Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh.

LaQshya, which stands for Labour Room Quality Improvement Initiative, is a flagship program launched by the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India, in 2017. The primary objective of the LaQshya Programme is to reduce maternal and neonatal mortality and morbidity by improving the quality of care in labor rooms and maternity operation theatres in public health facilities [1]. The initiative focuses on ensuring continuous training and capacity building for health care providers [2].

Respectful Maternal Care is an approach that emphasizes the provision of care that respects the dignity, privacy, and autonomy of women during childbirth. It involves practices such as maintaining the confidentiality of the mother, obtaining informed consent, allowing the presence of a birth companion, providing continuous emotional support, and ensuring non-discriminatory care [3].

The World Health Organization (WHO) has identified RMC as a key component of quality maternal care, highlighting its role in improving the overall childbirth experience and health outcomes for mothers and newborn.

The LaQshya Programme incorporates RMC principles into its framework to ensure that women receive respectful and dignified care during childbirth. This involves training healthcare providers on RMC practices, improving labor room infrastructure to ensure privacy and comfort, and establishing protocols for continuous monitoring and evaluation of care quality [4]. The programme also emphasizes the importance of involving the community and families in maternal care to enhance support systems for women [5]

The Implementation of RMC under the LaQshya Programme represents a significant step towards improving the quality of maternal care in India. By focusing on respectful and dignified care, the program aims to enhance maternal satisfaction and health outcomes. This study will provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of RMC practices and identify areas for further improvement, contributing to the overall goal of reducing maternal and neonatal mortality and morbidity.

OBJECTIVES

Primary objective

- To evaluate the level of respectful maternity care.

Secondary objective

- To improve quality of maternity care provided under laqshya programme based on outcome of the study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was designed as a cross-sectional observational study to capture a snapshot of the satisfaction levels of mothers who delivered at tertiary care centre after the implementation of Respectful Maternal Care (RMC) practices under the LaQshya Programme.

The study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology at Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose Medical College and Hospital, Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh. NSCB MCH is a prominent tertiary care hospital in the region, offering extensive maternal and child health services. The Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology is well-equipped with modern facilities and staffed by experienced healthcare professionals, making it an ideal setting for evaluating the impact of the LaQshya Programme on maternal satisfaction.

The study was conducted over an 18-month period, from July 15, 2021, to January 15, 2023.

Inclusion Criteria:

The study included all women who delivered in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology at Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose Medical College and Hospital, Jabalpur, during the study period from July 15, 2021, to January 15, 2023.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Mentally ill Patients
- Patients Who Denied Participation
- Critically Ill Patients

Data collection and procedures:

Participants were recruited systematically. Upon admission and after delivery, eligible patients were approached by trained research staff who explained the purpose of the study, procedures, potential benefits, and risks. Patients who agreed to participate were asked to sign an informed consent form.

Data from participants were collected using a structured questionnaire. This questionnaire included both closed and open-ended questions designed to capture comprehensive information about the participants' experiences and satisfaction levels. The data collection process was carried out in a manner that ensured the privacy and comfort of the participants. The questionnaires were filled out in the presence of a researcher or a trained staff member who could assist if necessary, ensuring clarity and completeness of responses.

Systematic random sampling was employed to select participants for this study. This method was chosen to ensure that every eligible mother who delivered at this hospital during the study period had an equal chance of being included in the sample.

Thus, the calculated sample size was approximately 1067.

This study did not involve distinct study groups as it primarily aimed to assess the overall satisfaction of all mothers who delivered at tertiary care. However, for analytical purposes, the data were stratified based on certain key demographic and clinical characteristics, such as age, parity, mode of delivery, and presence of antenatal complications. This approach helped to identify specific factors influencing maternal satisfaction and to understand variations in satisfaction levels among different groups of mothers, thereby providing deeper insights into the effectiveness of the RMC practices under the LaQshya Programme.

The results of the data analysis were then compiled and interpreted to draw meaningful conclusions about the effectiveness of RMC practices under the LaQshya Programme and to provide recommendations for further improvement.

OBSERVATION AND RESULT

Socio demographic details

Table 1: Distribution of cases according to the age

AGE	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
18-22 years	181	16.9%
22-25 years	450	42%
26-29 years	288	24.1%
30- 33years	157	14.7%
34 -37 years	15	1.5%
>38 years	6	0.6%
Total	1067	

Table 2: Distribution of cases according to socioeconomic status

SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS		
Lower class	567	53.1%
Middle Class	368	31.6%
Upper class	162	15.18%
Urban	280	26.2%
Rural	787	73%
Total	1067	100%

Graph 1: Distribution of cases according to age

The study “A Study to Evaluate Satisfaction After Implementation of Respectful Maternity Care Under LaQshya Programme” involved a diverse age range of participants (1067), with the majority (42%) being in the 22-25 years age group. Participants aged 26-29 years constituted 24.1%, while those aged 18-22 years made up 16.9%. Smaller

percentages were observed in the older age groups: 14.7% for 30-33 years, 1.5% for 34-37 years, and 0.6% for participants older than 38 years. This distribution highlights that the LaQshya program predominantly engaged younger women, particularly those in their early twenties, reflecting the target demographic for maternal care services.

Graph 2: Distribution of cases according to socioeconomic status

Most of the participants from our study belongs to lower socioeconomic group (53.1%). And came from rural areas (73%), while few of the participants are from urban areas (26.2%).
Obstetrics details of the patient

Table 3: Distribution of cases according to parity and gestation age

Parity	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Primigravida	531	49.8%
2 nd gravida	289	27%
Multi gravida	247	23.2%
Booked	289	27.1%
Unbooked	778	72.9 %
Gestation Age		
Term (37-42 weeks)	795	74.5%
Preterm (<37 weeks)	211	19.7%
Postdated (>42 weeks)	61	5.7 %
Total	1067	100 %

Distribution of cases according to parity

Graph 3: Distribution of cases according to parity

Distribution of cases according to gestational age

Graph 4 : Distribution of cases according to gestation age of the patient

Regarding parity, nearly half (49.8%) of the participants were primigravida, indicating they were experiencing their first pregnancy. The second gravida group comprised 27% of participants, while those in their third pregnancy (third gravida) made up 10.6%. This data shows a significant representation of first-time mothers, which is crucial for evaluating the impact of the programme on maternal satisfaction, particularly among women who are new to the maternity care system. The study further analyzed the delivery methods of the participants, with a total of 1,067 women included. The majority of these women, 63%, had vaginal deliveries, while 36% underwent cesarean sections. This data provides insight into the delivery outcomes within the programme, showing a higher prevalence of vaginal births, which is often associated with shorter recovery times and fewer complications compared to cesarean sections.

The study also included data on the gestational age of the patients at the time of delivery. The majority of the participants, 74.5%, delivered at term. Preterm deliveries accounted for 19.7% of the cases, while 5.7% of the participants had postdated pregnancies. This distribution indicates that most deliveries occurred at the expected gestational age, with a smaller proportion of preterm and postdated deliveries.

Maternal risk factors

Table 4: Distribution of cases according to maternal risk factors and mode of delivery

Complications	Frequency	Percentage (%)
PIH	79	7.4%
Diabetes	18	1.6%
Preterm	12	1.03%
Anemia	74	6.9%
Oligohydramnios	50	4.6%
Severe pre eclampsia	66	6.1%
Others	321	30 %
None	447	49.8 %
Mode of delivery		
Vaginal delivery	672	63 %
Cesarian section	395	36 %

The study reported various maternal complications during the antenatal period. Pregnancy-induced hypertension (PIH) was noted in 7.4% of the participants, while 6.9% experienced anemia. Severe preeclampsia was observed in 6.1% of cases, and 4.6% had oligohydramnios. Diabetes affected 1.6% of the participants, and preterm complications were present in 1.03%. Other complications accounted for 30% of the cases, and nearly half of the participants (49.8%) did not experience any complications.

Patient's satisfaction with respect to respectful maternity care

Table 5: Distribution of cases according to patient's satisfaction score

Questionaree	Score	Frequency (N=1067)	Percentage (%)
Time taken for registration of the patient	1	119	11.15%
	2	130	12.18%
	3	67	6.2%
	4	747	70%
	5	4	0.28%
Display of signage	1	181	11.26%
	2	182	11.3%
	3	62	3.8%
	4	642	39.5%
Availability of beds and clean bedsheets	1	212	19.86%
	2	125	11.6%
	3	669	62.6%
	4	61	5.7%
	5	00	0%
Daily meal plans in hospitals	1	112	4.8%
	2	98	9.18%
	3	47	4.8%
	4	810	75.9%
Availability of aya bai	1	151	14.1%
	2	88	8.24%
	3	783	73.3%
	4	42	3.9%
	5	3	0.28%
Time taken for initiation of treatment	15-1/2 hour	313	29.3%
	½hrs -1 hour	428	40.1%
	1 hour -2 hour	282	26.4%
	>2 hours	44	4.1%
Presence of abusive behaviour	Yes	60	5.62 %
	No	1007	94.37%
Mainataince of adequate privacy they received during labor	Yes	973	91%
	No	94	8.8%
Information regarding delivery	Yes	1005	94%
	No	62	5.8%
Availability of birth companion	Yes	1004	94%
	No	63	5.9%
Initiation of breastfeeding after delivery	30-1/2 hrs	80	7.4%
	½ hrs -1 hrs	75	7.02 %
	1 hrs – 2 hrs	295	27.6%
	>2 hrs	617	57.8%

Contraceptive advice they received	Yes	834	78.1%
	No	233	21.8 %
Total		1067	100%

Patient 's satisfaction in respect to respectful maternity care

The study assessed patient satisfaction with the registration facility through a questionnaire. The majority of participants, 70%, gave score of 3. A smaller percentage, 12.18%, rated the facility with a score of 2, and 11.15% gave a score of 1. Scores of 4 and 5 were less common, with 6.2% and 0.28% of participants, respectively, rating the facility at these higher levels.

The study also evaluated patient satisfaction with the information provided on how to reach the facility. The highest percentage of participants, 39.5%, gave a score of 3. Scores of 2 and 1 were given by 11.3% and 11.26% of participants, respectively. Only 3.8% rated the information with a score of 4, and no participants gave a score of 5.

Patient satisfaction regarding the availability of beds and clean bedsheets. The majority of participants, 62.6%, gave a score of 3, indicating moderate satisfaction. A significant portion, 19.86%, gave a score of 1, showing dissatisfaction. Additionally, 11.6% of participants rated this aspect with a score of 2, and 5.7% gave a score of 4. No of participants awarded the highest score of 5.

The study evaluated patient satisfaction with the food supply provided during their stay. The majority of participants, 75.9%, gave a score of 3, indicating a generally positive but moderate level of satisfaction. Scores of 1 and 2 were given by 4.8% and 9.18% of participants, respectively, reflecting some dissatisfaction. Additionally, 4.8% of participants rated the food supply with a score of 4, indicating a higher level of satisfaction.

Satisfaction with the availability of wheelchairs and ward boy assistance. The majority of participants, 73.38%, were moderately satisfied. A significant portion, 14.15%, expressed dissatisfaction. Additionally, 8.24% found the service somewhat unsatisfactory, while 3.93% were more satisfied with the assistance provided. Only a very small fraction, 0.28%, gave the highest possible satisfaction rating.

The majority of participants, 73.3%, were moderately satisfied with the availability of aya bai. A significant portion, 14.15%, expressed dissatisfaction. Additionally, 8.24% found the service somewhat unsatisfactory, while 3.93% were more satisfied with the assistance provided. Only a very small fraction, 0.28%, gave the highest possible satisfaction rating.

The study also assessed the time taken for initiation of registration. The largest group of participants, 40.1%, reported receiving assistance within 30 minutes to 1 hour. Another 29.3% received assistance within 15 to 30 minutes. A significant portion, 26.4%, waited between 1 to 2 hours, and 4.1% waited for more than 2 hours.

The study also examined the incidence of abuse during delivery. A vast majority of participants, 94.37%, reported not experiencing any abuse during their delivery. However, 5.62% of the participants did report facing abuse. The study also evaluated whether women felt they had adequate privacy during their stay. A significant majority, 91%, reported having adequate privacy, while 8.8% felt they did not have sufficient privacy.

The study also assessed whether women received adequate information regarding their delivery. A vast majority, 94%, reported that they were provided with sufficient information about their delivery process. Conversely, 5.8% of the participants felt that they did not receive adequate information.

The study evaluated the availability of a birth companion during the delivery process. A large majority of participants, 94.09%, reported having a birth companion present. In contrast, 5.9% of the women indicated that they did not have a birth companion available.

The study assessed the timing of breastfeeding initiation after delivery among participants. The findings revealed that 7.4% of women began breastfeeding within 30 minutes to half an hour, and 7.02% initiated breastfeeding within half an hour to one hour. A larger proportion, 27.64%, started breastfeeding within one to two hours after delivery. However, the majority, 57.8%, initiated breastfeeding after more than two hours. These results indicate that while some women were able to start breastfeeding relatively soon after delivery, most experienced a delay of more than two hours, highlighting an area for improvement to promote earlier initiation of breastfeeding for better newborn health outcomes.

The study also evaluated whether participants received contraceptive advice. The results showed that 78.1% of women reported receiving contraceptive advice, while 21.8% indicated that they did not receive any advice on contraception. This indicates that while the majority of women were provided with information on contraception, there remains a significant proportion who did not receive this essential advice, suggesting an area for improvement in postnatal care services.

A vast majority of participants, 94.37%, reported not experiencing any abuse during their delivery. However, 5.62% of the participants did report facing abuse.

Majority, 91%, reported having adequate privacy, while 8.8% felt they did not have sufficient privacy. 94% reported that they were provided with sufficient information about their delivery process, while 5.8% of the participants felt that they did not receive adequate information, 94.09% reported having a birth companion present. In contrast, 5.9% of the women indicated that they did not have a birth companion available.

As per above table 7.4% of women began breastfeeding within 30 Minutes to half an hour, and 7.02% initiated breastfeeding within half an hour to one hour. A larger proportion, 27.64%, started breastfeeding within one to two hours after delivery. However, the majority, 57.8%, initiated breastfeeding after more than two hours.

DISCUSSION

Respectful maternity care prioritizes the dignity, privacy, and rights of women during childbirth, in line with global standards for quality healthcare. This study examines the satisfaction levels of women who received maternity care at a tertiary care centre as part of the LaQshya programme and also focuses on the adherence to the principles related to healthcare practices and the resulting impact on the quality of maternity care. A total of 1067 participants were selected.

In our study majority of participants falls between 22-25 years (42%) and 26-29 years (24.1%). This study was in collaboration with the study conducted by Pramanik S et al. (2021) in West Bengal, where the mean age of the participants was 24.18 years.

Our study also found similar results, with a significant number of participants being from younger age groups reflecting predominantly younger women in the early twenties as target population for maternal care services under LaQshya programme.

In our study majority of the participants belongs to lower socioeconomic groups and from rural areas (63.1%), similar study conducted in Odisha, Yadav et al.(2022), had most of the participants belonging to middle class group (63.8%) followed by low socioeconomic group (11.8%)[6], our hospital is the only tertiary care hospital near to rural areas, and most of the patients we got are referred from near by hospitals.

In our study the distribution of parity among participants in this study reveals that almost half (49.8%) were primi patients, followed by 27% who were on second gravida and multigravida were 23%.

A recent study by Yadav et al. (2022) revealed that women who were pregnant for the second time generally had more positive experiences with reproductive and maternal healthcare[7]. In a study conducted at Pravara Rural Hospital, Bangal et al. (2020) found that women who were pregnant for the third time reported higher satisfaction scores (4.3 out of 5) with the practices of the hospital[8]. This can be attributed to their previous experiences with the healthcare system and childbirth, which enable them to have better communication and receive improved care during subsequent deliveries. There is a significant representation of first time mothers, which is crucial for evaluating the impact of the programme on maternal satisfaction, particularly among women who are new to the maternity care system.

In our study majority of the participants were unbooked (72.9%) and was referred from nearby CHC, PHC, and district hospitals.

In our study we found that the majority of deliveries occurred at term gestation (74.5%), while a smaller percentage of deliveries were preterm delivery (19.7%), while smaller percentage (5.7%) had post term deliveries. In a recent study, Kaur et al. (2022) discovered that women who gave birth at full term had more positive experiences with their medical care [9]. Yadav et al. (2022) revealed that postdated and preterm deliveries were associated with lower satisfaction scores [10].

Term deliveries tend to be associated with more positive care experiences compared to preterm and postdated deliveries. In our study various maternal risk factors during pregnancy, including pregnancy-induced hypertension (PIH) at 7.4%, diabetes at 1.6%, preterm delivery at 1.03%, anemia at 6.9%, oligohydraminos at 4.6%, severe preeclampsia at 6.1%, was seen and in 49.8% there was no complications. Kaur et al. (2022) observed that women with complications such as

PIH and anemia experienced higher levels of disrespect and abuse during labor. Specifically, their study found that 8% of women with PIH and 7% of women with anemia reported mistreatment during childbirth (Kaur et al., 2022) [11]. Similarly, Yadav et al. (2022) found that severe pre-eclampsia was significantly associated with mistreatment and poor maternity care in Eastern India [12].

In our study majority of women had vaginal delivery (63%), while a significant portion had cesarean sections (36%). In comparison, similar studies have shown that satisfaction and outcomes can differ depending on the method of delivery. As an example, a study conducted by Karoni et al. (2020) found that maternal satisfaction-rates were higher for vaginal deliveries (65.6%) compared to cesarean sections (57.2%) in Bahir Dar, Ethiopia (Karoni et al., 2020)[13]. In addition, a study conducted by Kumar and Dhillon (2020) in India revealed that an early discharge after a cesarean section was associated with reduced postnatal care and increased complications (Kumar & Dhillon, 2020 [14].

These studies highlight the significance of enhancing delivery practices and postnatal care to enhance maternal satisfaction and outcomes across various delivery methods.

For the registration facility, 70% of patients gave a score of 4, indicating good satisfaction. A study findings by Sharma et al. (2019) where many patients reported inadequacies in registration procedures in Uttar Pradesh [15].

In our institution after implementation of LaQshya programme, separate registration counter has been opened for ANC patients, which made easy registration of the patient.

For the display of signage information, 39.5% rated it a 4, reflecting good satisfaction score, which aligns with Rajbangshi et al. (2022) in Assam, where accessibility issues were prevalent (Rajbangshi et al., 2022)[16]. Under LaQshya program various signage information in form of photos and arrows were provided.

Concerning the availability of beds and clean bedsheets, majority 62.6% rated it a 3 showing moderate satisfaction, same findings by Tripathi et al. (2019) who noted similar issues in private sector facilities across multiple states [17]. The lack of clean bed and bed sheets arise due to higher patient load and lack of staff. The issue was highlighted and under LaQshya programme, wards and more no of beds were made available and staff was recruited, which improved patients satisfaction.

In our study Regarding the satisfaction score obtained on the daily meal plan provided by the hospital, 75.9% rated their satisfaction as 4 showing good satisfaction another study findings by Okumu and Oyugi (2018) in Kenya, where food quality in public hospitals was a concern, impacting overall patient satisfaction.

In our study patient satisfaction regarding wheelchair and ward boy facilities was evaluated, showing that 73.38% of women rated these services with a score of 3, indicating moderate satisfaction. In a similar study, Das et al. (2021) reported that patient satisfaction scores improved from 82.5% to 95.5% after implementing quality improvement measures in public health facilities in Haryana, emphasizing the importance of supportive staff and adequate resources [18].

In our study the time taken for initiation of treatment was assessed and found that a significant percentage of women were initiated within various time frames. Majority (40.1%) of women were started treatment within ½ hour to 1 hour, 29.3% within 15 minutes to ½ hour, 26.4% within 1 to 2 hours, and 4.1% in more than 2 hours. Kumar and Dhillon (2020) [19]. emphasized the importance of timely registration and initiation of treatment in improving maternal outcomes. They found that delays in treatment can cause increased anxiety and dissatisfaction among patients, with 30% of women reporting such delays. These studies highlight the significance of decreasing registration time and early initiation of treatment to enhance overall patient satisfaction and care quality in maternity services.

In our study a small percentage of women, (5.62%) experienced abuse during labour, while the majority, 94.37%, did not report any abuse. Sharma et al. (2019) discovered that a high percentage of women in Uttar Pradesh faced mistreatment during labour [20]. This included non-dignified care, verbal abuse, and even physical abuse, with a prevalence rate of 28.8%. These studies highlight the significant problem of mistreatment and abuse during labour in India, emphasizing the urgent requirement for interventions to promote respectful maternity care. After the implementation of LaQshya programme in 2018, the concept of respectful maternity care and child birth has become an integral component of antenatal and intranatal care resulting in only small no. of women facing abuse and good child birth experience.

In our study, the majority of women (91%) reported satisfaction with the level of privacy during labor. A recent study by Bharti et al. (2021) highlighted the positive impact of privacy during labor in New Delhi [21]. The use of curtains were found to significantly improve privacy for expectant mothers.

After LaQshya implementation, in our institution adequate privacy was ensured for the labouring women in the form of curtains. Which women gave overall good satisfaction score.

As per our study, the majority of women (94%) was satisfied with the information given about their delivery, while a small percentage (5.8%) did not. In a study conducted by Sharma et al. (2019), it was discovered that when women were given sufficient information during delivery, their overall satisfaction increased and their anxiety was decreased. 90% of women reported feeling satisfied when they were properly informed [22]. Also in our study the majority of women, 94.09%, had a birth companion present during labour and delivery. A recent study conducted by Bharti et al. (2021) emphasized the positive impact of having a birth companion during labour. The findings revealed that 75% of women reported feeling more secure and supported when accompanied by a companion (Bharti et al., 2021) [23]. In a study conducted across 18 public hospitals in India, Singh et al. (2021) discovered a similar finding. They observed that having a birth companion during labour had a significant impact on reducing disrespect and abuse [24]. The study revealed that only 5% of women experienced mistreatment when accompanied by a birth companion, compared to 20% of women who did not have one. Presence of birth companion during labour helps in reducing the stress and improving the overall birth experience. The birth companion also reduces the burden on the staff for continuous watchfulness.

In our study it was found that 57.8% of women-initiated breastfeeding more than 2 hours after delivery, with only 7.4% starting within 30 minutes to ½ hour and 27.64% within 1 to 2 hours. This delay is concerning and consistent with other studies. Mary et al. (2021) found that less than half of new mothers practiced early initiation of breastfeeding (EIBF) within one hour, major cause of such delays were attributed to factors such as caesarian sections and inadequate maternal knowledge [(Mary et al., 2021) [25]]. These results highlight the need for timely initiation of breastfeeding and adequate counselling by the staff after delivery of the patient. This delay in our study as well as other study can be attributed to lack of counselling and awareness of new mother and inadequacy of staff and it must be addressed on urgent basis.

In our study, 78% of participants received contraceptive advice. This study highlights the importance of contraceptive advice that should be given by the doctors and nurses. Patient should be counselled and informed about various methods of contraception available and their importance throughout her ANC period and during labour. This result highlights the need of contraceptive counselling in improving maternal and neonatal health outcomes.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the implementation and outcomes of respectful maternity care under the LaQshya Programme. A large number of participants were young women, mostly experiencing their first pregnancy, with a considerable proportion giving birth vaginally at full term. While there are some aspects of registration, directions, bed availability, and food supply that have been moderately satisfactory, there are still areas that need significant improvement. The concerning rate of delayed initiation of breastfeeding and the significant number of women not receiving timely contraceptive advice highlight the importance of improving postnatal care practices. In addition, the instances of mistreatment during childbirth, although reported by a smaller number of people, highlight the urgent requirement for interventions that prioritize dignified and respectful care. The positive aspects of ensuring privacy and allowing birth companions were observed, highlighting the valuable impact of these supportive measures on patient experiences. In order to address the identified gaps and enhance the overall quality of maternity care, it is crucial to prioritize continuous training for healthcare providers, allocate resources more effectively, and establish strong monitoring mechanisms. These steps are essential in guaranteeing that every woman receives the caring, considerate, and top-notch care they are entitled to during childbirth.

REFERENCES

1. Kok BD. Global maternal health: from women's survival to respectful care. *BJOG*. 2015;122.
2. Stones W. Respectful care in labour. *Obstet Gynaecol Reprod Med*. 2016; 26:341-342.
3. Mousa O, Turingan OM. Quality of care in the delivery room: Focusing on respectful maternal care practices. *J Nurs Educ Pract*. 2018; 9(1):1-7.
4. Gurung R, Ruysen H, Sunny AK, Day L, Penn-Kekana L, Målvqvist M, et al. Respectful maternal and newborn care: measurement in one ENBIRTH study hospital in Nepal. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth*. 2021; 21:735.
5. Daniel G, Afolaranmi T, Ari ES, Yafeh AM, Dioso R. Women's Voices, Women's Realities; Experiences of Respectful Maternity Care During Childbirth in Jos, Nigeria. *Malays J Nurs*. 2023; 15(2):33-39.
6. Yadav, P., Smitha, M. V., Jacob, J., & Begum, J. (2022). Intrapartum respectful maternity care practices and its barriers in Eastern India. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, 11(12), 7657–7663.
7. Bangal, V. B., Vikhe, S., Borhade, S., & Thorat, U. (2020). Respectful maternity care for positive birthing experience at Pravara Rural Hospital. *International Journal of Reproduction, Contraception, Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 9(8), 3297.
8. Kaur, M., Gogoi, A., Manoranjini, M., Ravi, T., Gupta, M., & Rajagopal, V. (2022). Determinants of respectful maternity care in India: A cross-sectional study. *WHO South-East Asia Journal of Public Health*.

9. Karoni, H. F., Bantie, G. M., Azage, M., Semachew Kasa, A., Aynie, A. A., & Tsegaye, G. W. (2020). Maternal satisfaction among vaginal and cesarean section delivery care services in Bahir Dar city health facilities, Northwest Ethiopia: A facility-based comparative cross-sectional study. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*, 20, 473.
10. Rajbangshi, P. R., Srivastava, A., & Nambiar, D. (2022). Women's experiences with maternity care in public health facilities of Assam, India: a qualitative study. *South-East Asia Journal of Public Health*, 11(1), 61–64
11. Tripathi, S., Srivastava, A., Memon, P., et al. (2019). Quality of maternity care provided by private sector healthcare facilities in three states of India: a situational analysis. *BMC Health Services Research*, 19, 971.
12. Das, S. D., Kapoor, A. P., Kumar, D., Gupta, M., et al. (2021). Improving quality of care for pregnancy, perinatal and newborn care at district and sub-district public health facilities in Haryana, India: An implementation study. *BMC Health Services Research*, 21, 726.
13. Kumar, P., & Dhillon, P. (2020). Length of stay after childbirth in India: A comparative study of public and private health institutions. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*, 20, 181.
14. Sharma, G., Penn-Kekana, L., Halder, K., & Filippi, V. (2019). An investigation into mistreatment of women during labour and childbirth in maternity care facilities in Uttar Pradesh, India: A mixed-methods study. *Reproductive Health*, 16, 7.
15. Bharti, J., Kumari, A., Zangmo, R., Mathew, S., Kumar, S., & Sharma, A.K. (2021). Establishing the practice of birth companion in labour ward of a tertiary care centre in India—a quality improvement initiative. *BMJ Open Quality*, 10(Suppl 1): e001409.
16. Singh, S., Goel, R., Gogoi, A., Varkey, L. C., Manoranjini, M., Ravi, T., & Rawat, D. (2021). Presence of birth companion—a deterrent to disrespectful behaviours towards women during delivery: An exploratory mixed-method study in 18 public hospitals of India. *Health Policy and Planning*, 36(10), 1552–1561.
17. Mary, J. J. F., Sindhuri, R., Kumaran, A. A., & Dongre, A. R. (2022). Early initiation of breastfeeding and factors associated with its delay among mothers at discharge from a tertiary care hospital. *Clinical and Experimental Pediatrics*, 65(4), 201–208.